

EXPLORING (EMERGING) MYCOTOXINS RISK IN BEANS: A GLOBAL ALLIANCE FOR CLIMATE CHANGE RESILIENCE

D5.1 – Data Management Plan

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COORDINATOR	Chiara Dall'Asta (UNIPR)
ADDRESS	Department of Food and Drug, Viale delle Scienze 27/A, 43124 Parma, Italy
E-MAIL	chiara.dallasta@unipr.it
PHONE	+39 0521 905669
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RESPONSIBLE AUTHOR	Chiara Dall'Asta (UNIPR)
E-MAIL	chiara.dallasta@unipr.it
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AUTHORS (PARTNER)	Chiara Dall'Asta (UNIPR)
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HISTORY OF CHANGES

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1.0	Initial Version	22/04/2024	Chiara Dall'Asta (UNIPR)
2.0	Update	08.02.2026	Chiara Dall'Asta (UNIPR)

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The DMP is maintained as a living document and is periodically updated to reflect the actual data types generated or reused, the repositories effectively adopted, and the data governance procedures implemented across the consortium. The present update focuses on clarifying data flows between internal working environments and public repositories, formalising access control and approval mechanisms, and reinforcing compliance with FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable).

Public project outputs, including deliverables, publications, training materials and eligible datasets, are deposited in the dedicated MYCOBEANS Zenodo community, ensuring persistent identifiers, long-term preservation and open accessibility. Internal working data and preliminary datasets are managed through a controlled institutional OneDrive environment hosted by the University of Parma and shared with WP and task leaders, supporting secure collaboration prior to public release.

Sequencing data generated by associated partners are temporarily stored in secure institutional repositories during quality control and validation phases and will be transferred to appropriate international domain repositories (e.g. ENA/SRA) once datasets are finalised. Decisions on data release, access level and timing are governed by WP leaders in coordination with the Project Coordinator.

Unless otherwise justified, public datasets are released under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) licence. Personal data are collected only when strictly necessary, handled in compliance with GDPR, and retained for a limited period exclusively for auditing and accountability purposes.

Overall, this DMP update confirms that MYCOBEANS data are managed under a robust, transparent and controlled governance model, ensuring Open Science compliance, data integrity and long-term reusability throughout and beyond the project duration.

Mycobbeans DMP

This updated version of the MYCOBEANS Data Management Plan (DMP) consolidates the transition from an initial framework to an operational and monitored data management system.

The DMP remains a living document, periodically revised to reflect the actual data types generated and reused, the repositories effectively adopted, and the governance procedures implemented across the consortium.

The present update focuses on: (i) clarification of data flows and storage locations (internal vs public), (ii) explicit mapping between data types and trusted repositories (e.g., Zenodo and domain-specific repositories when applicable), (iii) refined access rules (“as open as possible, as closed as necessary”) and licensing choices, and (iv) strengthened operational provisions for data security and GDPR-compliant handling of personal data.

Overall, the DMP confirms that MYCOBEANS data are managed under a controlled governance model, ensuring FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and long-term preservation for at least five years after the end of the project.

Changes since version 1.0

Since version 1.0, the DMP has been updated to reflect the operational data management practices effectively adopted by the consortium. The following changes are introduced to improve clarity, traceability and compliance:

- *Repository mapping clarified:* generic references to “open cloud environments” are replaced by an explicit mapping of each data type to an appropriate trusted repository (e.g., Zenodo for project outputs; domain repositories for sequencing or omics data when applicable).
- *Internal vs public data flows separated:* internal working data and sensitive materials are explicitly managed in restricted consortium spaces (e.g., SharePoint), while public outputs are disseminated through the project website and repositories with persistent identifiers (DOIs).

- *Access rules operationalised*: the principle “as open as possible, as closed as necessary” is retained but translated into concrete access categories (public / embargoed / restricted / closed) and approval rules for restricted access requests.
- *Licensing made explicit*: default licences (e.g., Creative Commons) are assigned by data/output type, with justified exceptions where IPR or partner constraints apply.
- *Personal data governance tightened*: personal data categories, purpose limitation, retention, and access control are made explicit and aligned with GDPR provisions already stated in v1.0.

List of repositories in use

- Zenodo MYCOBEANS community:
<https://zenodo.org/communities/mycobeans/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>
- GitHub (for bioinformatics pipeline implementation)
- Internal repository on MS365 OneDrive maintained by UNIPR

Data Summary

Table X. Data types, repositories, access and reuse conditions (operational mapping)

Data / Output type	Examples in MYCOBEANS	Primary storage (internal)	Public repository (if applicable)	Access level	PID/Metadata	Retention	Licence
Public deliverables	Reports, plans	SharePoint: OneDrive	Zenodo community	Public	DOI + metadata template	≥5y after project end	CC BY 4.0
Publications	OA papers	Partner institutional systems	Journal/Repo + Zenodo (when allowed)	Public	DOI	permanent	publisher/OA terms
LC–MS(/MS) raw & processed data	chromatograms, quant tables	Partner servers + SharePoint	Zenodo MYCOBEANS community	Restricted	DOI + metadata file (.txt)	≥5y after project end	Restricted / Embargoed (until publication)
Sequencing data	Illumina/Nanopore reads	Partner servers	ENA/SRA	Embargo	accession + rich metadata	permanent	standard repo terms
Training materials	slides, videos	SharePoint	Website + Zenodo	Public	DOI optional	≥5y after project end	CC BY 4.0
Personal data (GDPR)	secondees, event participants	Restricted SharePoint folder	Not public			4y after project end	

Public repositories and Open science

Public project outputs, including public deliverables, reports, training materials and eligible datasets, are deposited in the dedicated [MYCOBEANS Zenodo community](#), which serves as the primary trusted repository for long-term preservation, persistent identifiers (DOIs) and FAIR compliance.

Internal repositories and workflows

Internal working data, preliminary datasets and restricted materials are managed through a dedicated institutional OneDrive (Office365) environment hosted by the University of Parma (UNIPR) and shared with all WP leaders and task leaders. The institutional OneDrive environment is managed under UNIPR IT security policies, including controlled access, authentication, regular backups and compliance with institutional data protection standards.

This environment is used for controlled internal data exchange, versioning and collaborative work during data generation and validation phases, prior to public dissemination.

Sequencing data

Sequencing data generated by associated partners in Thailand are currently stored in secure internal institutional repositories, in accordance with local data governance and infrastructure policies.

Once datasets are quality-checked, validated and finalised (“data freeze”), sequencing data will be transferred to an appropriate international domain repository (e.g. ENA/SRA), ensuring long-term preservation, standardised metadata and public accessibility in line with FAIR principles.

Temporary internal storage prior to deposition in ENA/SRA is limited to the period required for quality control, metadata curation and scientific validation, and does not represent a restriction of access beyond what is scientifically justified.

Access control and data approval

Decisions regarding data release, access level (public, embargoed or restricted) and timing of dissemination are jointly taken by the relevant WP leader(s) and the Project Coordinator.

This approval mechanism ensures consistency with scientific validation status, intellectual property considerations and ethical obligations.

Licensing

Unless otherwise justified, public datasets and project outputs are released under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) licence, allowing broad reuse with appropriate attribution.

Personal data (GDPR)

Personal data are collected and processed only when strictly necessary for project implementation (e.g. secondments, training events, reporting and auditing obligations). The four-year retention period is aligned with Horizon Europe auditing requirements and institutional policies, after which personal data will be securely deleted or anonymised.

Such data are stored with restricted access and retained for a period of four years after the end of the project, solely for auditing and accountability purposes, in full compliance with GDPR requirements.